

LAST PART OF OPTIMIZATION OF THE IC-ESI-MS AND
FIRST PART OF THE VALIDATION OF THE CATION
METHOD FOR FUTURE FORENSIC CASE WORK

THE NETHERLANDS FORENSIC INSTITUTE

Author: Shanaya S. Soeknandan
Student ID: 120308
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Supervisor: Mr. Carlos Martín Alberca
Examiner: Mr. Chung Wong
Mentor: Mr Bas Tawil

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1 Introduction

At the NFI the explosion and explosives team developed a new method to analyse pre- and post-blast pyrotechnic fireworks and explosives. The new technique, the IC-ESI-MS, will be used to analyse inorganic explosives. One of the developed methods was focused on the cations. The aim is to optimize the instrument and validate this method and apply this to forensic case work.

As part of the validation several experiments should have been done. One of the experiments, defining a linear range for the 18 cations of interest, is explained in this document. Parallel to this experiment some results have been recovered and observed about a blank study.

Each analyte has its own linear range. This study is based on finding out the linearity of a selected group of cations. To find the advisable linearity of each cation, an experiment must be carried out. When designing an experiment like this several issues arise. For example, what range of concentration should be used, what is the limit of detection (LOD) of those ions, what kind of sample should be analysed, how to process the data. The aim is to obtain as much information as possible about the linear range of each ion. The outcome of this experiment can be used in the validation process of the IC-ESI-MS.

As part of this assignment a manual is written by the author about the use of the IC-ESI-MS. This work instruction will be submitted to the examiner separately from this document.

Last part of the optimization of the IC-ESI-MS and first part of the validation of the cation method for future forensic case work

Author: S. S. Soeknandan 120308
The Netherlands Forensic Institute

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2 Instrument

The Ion Chromatography Electrospray Ionization Mass spectrometer (IC-ESI-MS) with a single quadrupole is a very sensitive instrument. The MS separates on the different masses of the ions. Each ion has several masses also called channels. In the developing process several methods have been created including the one currently using in the validation process of the cations. The MS method has preprogrammed retention time windows for each ion of interest. These windows have been made based on the retention time of the ions. So, the ions should elute within this window otherwise there will be no peak visible in the chromatograms.

Figure 1 IC-ESI-MS used for the validation of the cation part and for this experiment.

2.1 Parameters of the method

For an analysis there are several important parameters. These parameters have been optimized as part of the method development.

Table 1 Parameters of the method

IC-ESI-MS	Eluent:	4,9mM Oxalic acid + 25% Acetonitrile
	Flow:	1 ml/min
	Pressure:	14,7 MPa
	Column temperature:	30 °C
	Method	Isocratic
	Running time:	26 min
	Desolvation gas:	1200L/Hr
	Desolvation temperature:	350°C
	Capillary Voltage:	1KV
	Column:	cation-exchange column (250 x 4.0 mm)
	Sample loop:	20 µl

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The Netherlands Forensic Institute

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2.2 Specification instrument

- IC Methrom 850
- Auto sampler 919 Plus
 - o Capacity 56
- Waters Mass spectrometer Zspray ESI, Single Quadrupole
- UPLC pump
- Detector
- Suppressor
- Guard column
- Column Methrom, cation-exchange column (250 x 4.0 mm)
- Ventilation pump

3 Chemicals

- Oxalic Acid, from Sigma Alridch, 98% CAS 144-62-7
- Acetonitrile from Biosolve, ULC/MS-CC/SFC grade CAS 75-05-8
- Ultrapure water, (resistivity of 18.2 MΩ·cm at 21°C obtained from a Veolia Water ELGA system)
- Methanol from Biosolve, ULC/MS-CC/SFC grade CAS 67-56-1
- Isopropanol from Biosolve, LC-MS grade CAS 67-63-0
- Cations salts (multiple different suppliers)
- Isopropanol swabs, B. Braun

Table 2 Cations included in the validation

Cations included in the validation	
Lithium	Cadmium
Sodium	Cesium
Potassium	Copper
Magnesium	Zinc
Strontium	Aluminium
Lead	Ethylammonium
Barium	Dicyandiamide
Manganese	Ammonium
Calcium	Cobalt

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Optimizing the MS

As part of the method developing the MS should be optimized. This experiment was carried out by the author as part of the method developing and validation assignment. Optimizing the MS means finding out the right condition for the MS which results a good separation. The conditions such as the capillary voltage, desolvation gas and desolvation temperature were adjusted. A lot of combination of these conditions were used to find the right parameters.

After adjusting the settings of the MS, a standard of 18 cations at 1 ppm was analysed multiple times. After each testing the chromatogram was compared to a reference of the normal condition used so far. When viewing the chromatogram, were the desolvation temperature was at 650°C, the separation was worse than a separation at 350°C. This tells us the higher the temperature the worse the separation gets. Also, the less desolvation gas the worse the separation.

4.1.1 Results optimizing the MS

As the testing went on finally the optimal condition were found. To check whether this was the optimal conditions again several standards of 18 cations at 1 ppm were repeatably analysed. After viewing the chromatograms, it was clear that the condition was optimal, and the validation could have continued. The optimal conditions are: desolvation gas: 1200 L/Hr, desolvation temperature: 350°C, capillary voltage: 1KV.

4.2 Validation

Both spiked samples as the chemical blanks were analysed along with the calibration standards. As the quality rules says, after five analysis of unknown samples a standard should be analysed, to check whether the sensitivity is stable or not.

4.2.1 Calibration standards

The calibration curve consists of 9 standards and each is composed of 18 cations. The range varied between 0 and 10 ppm **Table 3**. The complex mix was made from individual stock solution (1000ppm). Next to the standards there are ten chemical blanks and ten spiked samples. Chemical blanks exist out of isopropanol swab (B Braun) with Ultrapure water. The reasons why chemical blanks are also taken in account is because there is a possibility that those isopropanol swabs contain traces of some ions.

The standards are made of 18 cations **Table 2** at the concentration described in **Table 3** with ultrapure water. For the preparation of the standards solutions glassware has been used. A hypothesis is that glassware may have an impact on the concentration of sodium.

4.2.2 The study

First a blank (Ultrapure water) was analysed and after that a standard of 18 cations which is used for daily check. After that a blank was analysed again to prevent cross contamination from the standard. Next the sequence started with the calibration standards followed by five spiked samples. Subsequently to that again the calibration standards were analysed. After the second calibration standards the remaining five spiked samples were analysed. Finally, the calibration standards were analysed for the third time. By analysing the calibration standard multiple times, it is possible to keep an eye on the sensitivity.

The following day the chemical blanks were analysed among the calibration standards. This time the calibration standards were analysed twice, at the beginning and at the end of the sequence. After the first five chemical blanks a standard of 2 ppm was analysed as a check. Next to that the remaining five chemical blanks and the calibrations standards were analysed.

Table 3 The standards with the concentration in the right column

Standard	Concentration in ppm
1	0
2	0,2
3	0,4
4	0,8
5	1
6	2
7	4
8	8
9	10

Table 4 The names of the chemical blanks and spiked samples. Later in the results and discussion chapter these names will be used.

Sample name chemical blanks	Sample name spiked samples
Chemical Blank 1	Spiked sample 1
Chemical Blank 2	Spiked sample 2
Chemical Blank 3	Spiked sample 3
Chemical Blank 4	Spiked sample 4
Chemical Blank 5	Spiked sample 5
Chemical Blank 6	Spiked sample 6
Chemical Blank 7	Spiked sample 7
Chemical Blank 8	Spiked sample 8
Chemical Blank 9	Spiked sample 9
Chemical Blank 10	Spiked sample 10

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Author: S. S. Soeknandan 120308
The Netherlands Forensic Institute

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Table 5 The 18 cations of interest with the LOD's.

Cation	LOD in ppb
Lithium	0,5
Sodium	0,9
Potassium	0,5
Magnesium	5
Strontium	80
Lead	400
Barium	600
Manganese	25
Calcium	50
Cobalt	12
Cadmium	275
Cesium	2,5
Copper	75
Zinc	250
Aluminium	80
Ethylammonium	30
Dicyandiamide	12
Ammonium	250

5 Processing data

The data of the spiked samples and the chemical blanks are processed with Targetlynx (Waters). With this software the peaks can be integrated manually. It is required that the signal to noise ratio (S/N) should be at least 3 or higher. If the S/N is below the 3 then the peak cannot be considered as a peak. In total there are three calibration curves individually made of the 18 cations. Because there is a huge amount of data, one sample of the spiked sample and the chemical blank is described. The remaining data can be found in **Appendix I and II**.

5.1 Processing data: spiked samples

While processing the recovered data of the spiked samples 8 out of the 18 cations were presents at a decent concentration.

Spiked sample 1: Determined which cations are present in this sample and at what concentration in part per million (ppm). The present ions are given a green colour. Zinc is an exception because it may look that there is Zinc present but when looking at the retention time and mass channels it's obvious that it is not a peak. While studying the data it became clearer that this instrument with this method is more sensitive to more particles with similar masses to the masses of the cations.

In **Table 6** the remaining ions are also listed because it gives an impression of there may have been an area, but it is not related to a peak. Also, the negative concentration also illustrate that those are not present. The data in **Chapter 10 Appendix I** only shows the present ions.

Table 6 Sample 1: the analytes which came back as positive. Green are the one how came back as positive. Zinc is an exception. The other ions came back as negative.

Spiked sample 1							
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Conc. III (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Zinc	66151	1,3	2,5	1,9	1,9	0,57	30%
Sodium	23033	5,8	7,2	5,1	6,0	1,07	18%
Potassium	11770052	2,7	4,0	3,6	3,4	0,67	20%
Magnesium	738973	4,2	6,6	6,0	5,6	1,23	22%
Strontium	873816	2,3	3,8	3,4	3,2	0,77	24%
Lead	2893	0,0	-0,1	-0,1	-0,1	0,06	-81%
Barium	248581	1,7	2,6	2,3	2,2	0,49	22%
Manganese	5805	-0,4	-0,5	-0,2	-0,3	0,16	-46%
Calcium	588789	1,9	2,6	2,1	2,2	0,38	17%
Cobalt		-0,2	-0,3	-0,2	-0,2	0,05	-23%
Cadmium	916	0,0	-0,1	0,1	0,0	0,13	-828%
Cesium	1401	0,0	0,0	0,1	0,1	0,05	101%
Copper	58152	-0,4	-0,2	-0,3	-0,3	0,12	-44%
Lithium	23007612	2,1	3,9	3,3	3,1	0,92	30%
Aluminium	520	-0,5	-0,6	-0,5	-0,5	0,06	-12%
Ethylammonium	37043	-1,7	-2,0	-2,5	-2,1	0,38	-19%
Dicyandiamide	726	-0,7	-0,7	-0,4	-0,6	0,14	-24%
Ammonium	23033	5,8	7,2	5,1	6,0	1,09	18%

5.2 Processing data: chemical blanks

While processing data from the chemical blanks few ions came back positive. Below chemical blank is shown. The remaining data of the chemical blanks can be found in **Chapter 10 Appendix I**

Chemical blank 1

In this blank a lot of sodium for a blank was present along with potassium and calcium in minority.

Table 7 Determined concentration of the cations in the chemical blank 1

Chemical blank 1						
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Sodium	3677508	2,2	2,4	2,3	0,15	6%
Potassium	2463011	0,5	0,6	0,6	0,06	10%
Calcium	6379	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,00	3%

Viewing the calibration curve of sodium (**Figure 2**) it is obvious that the selected range of 0 ppm to 10 ppm is not the linear range for sodium. This also applies for the first calibration curve. The correlation coefficient shows that there is a possible disagreement between the two variables. There are multiple outliers. If a smaller range is selected, then there is a possible linear range for sodium.

Figure 2 Second calibration curve of Sodium which was at the end of the sequence.

5.3 Processing data: statistics

Another part of processing data is taking a look to the statistics like standard deviation and relative standard deviation. The standard deviation says something about the differences in area or in concentration. A lower relative standard deviation indicates less difference in area or in concentration, depends on what the statistics are used on. The lower the relative standard deviation is the better. In **Table 6** the statistics on potassium in all ten spiked samples is shown. The relative standard deviation was used on the area and on the separate concentrations. Judging the results in **Table 6**, it can be said that there is a significant difference between the samples as in area as in concentration. This also applies for the rest of the cations.

Table 8 Statistics on all ten spiked samples, cation potassium.

<u>Spike samples</u> <u>Potassium</u>	Area	Conc. I	Conc. II	Conc. III
1	11770052	2,71	4,03	3,58
2	10256502	2,28	3,44	3,08
3	9763864	2,15	3,25	2,92
4	9129722	1,97	3,00	2,71
5	8827957	1,88	2,88	2,61
6	8018409	1,66	2,57	2,34
7	7662010	1,56	2,43	2,23
8	7339501	1,47	2,30	2,12
9	10176344	2,26	3,41	3,06
10	7233040	1,44	2,26	2,09
Average	9017740,10	1,94	2,96	2,68
Standard deviation	1410520,51	0,42	0,58	0,49
Relative standard deviation	16%	22%	20%	18%

5.4 Processing data: linear range

As expected the linear ranges is different for each cation. The range of the calibration standards started from 0 ppm still 10 ppm. While making the calibration curves it was clear that for some ions the linear range is smaller. For example, magnesium. Looking at **Figure 3** the correlation coefficient is closer to 1 than the correlation coefficient in **Figure 4**. Both curves are made of the standards. The difference is in the range of the concentration. Although magnesium shows with linear statistics a smaller range but perhaps in future quadratic equations could be used to define the range for magnesium. If quadratics statistics are used, then the range for magnesium or sodium will be wider. This also applies for lithium for example. In **Appendix 11 Figure 6 & 7** are also an example.

Figure 3 Calibration curve of spiked sample, cation magnesium. Linear range from 0-10ppm.

Figure 4 Calibration curve of spiked sample, cation magnesium. Linear range adjusted to 0-2ppm

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Author: S. S. Soeknandan 120308
The Netherlands Forensic Institute

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The advisable linear ranges of the 18 cations of interest

Table 9 The advisable linear ranges of the 18 cations. These ranges are based on this experiment

Cation	Linear range
Lithium	0 – 1 ppm
Sodium	0 – 2 ppm
Potassium	0 – 4 ppm
Magnesium	0 – 2 ppm
Strontium	0 – 10 ppm
Lead	0 – 10 ppm
Barium	0 – 10 ppm
Manganese	0 – 4 ppm
Calcium	0 – 10 ppm
Cobalt	0 – 10 ppm
Cadmium	0 – 10 ppm
Cesium	0 – 10 ppm
Copper	0 – 10 ppm
Zinc	0 – 1 ppm
Aluminium	0 – 8 ppm
Ethylammonium	0 – 0,8 ppm
Dicyandiamide	0 – 2 ppm
Ammonium	0 – 1 ppm

6 Conclusion

Defining a linear range for sodium is more difficult because sodium is also present in glassware used for the preparation of the solutions. For eleven out of the eighteen cations a different linear range is suitable see **Table 9**.

In the spiked samples the following ions such as ammonium, magnesium, sodium, potassium, calcium, barium & lithium were found at an approximately concentration of 2 ppm. Except for sodium. The concentration of sodium is higher because this is already present in the isopropanol swabs. **Chapter 12: Appendix III Figure 10 & 11**.

In the chemical blanks several masses were found but it's not clear to say that there are traces of magnesium or traces of iron. To be sure that there are traces of those ions, there should have been a peak in all channels of the masses. But in this case, there was only in one channel a peak visible.

6.1 Discussion for future work

- The integration of the peaks was done manually so there could be an error while integrating.
- Error in the retention time. The software could say that it is a peak, but the retention time does not match with the reference retention time. A better protocol must be set up for the expecting retention time.
- Use quadratic statistics for some ions to achieve a wider range of concentrations.

7 Author

This report is written by Shanaya S. Soeknandan supervised by Carlos Martín Alberca and Chris-Jan Kuijpers. This document is written in the period of March-April 2019. The author would like to thank the colleagues of the explosive team for the help and their efforts to realize this.

8 Acknowledgment

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9 Reference

[1] NFI internal document number SOP 161501.

[2] Validation plan IC-ESI-MS by Carlos Martín Alberca

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Author: S. S. Soeknandan 120308
The Netherlands Forensic Institute

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[3] Best practise manual for the Forensic Recovery Identification and Analysis of Explosives traces (European Commission)

10 Appendix I: Results

10.1 Data of spiked samples

Table 10 Determined concentration of the cations in spiked sample 2

Spiked sample 2							
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Conc. III (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Zinc	78905	1,8	3,1	2,4	2,5	0,63	26%
Sodium	8947306	4,74	6,96	6,26	6,0	1,13	19%
Potassium	10256502	2,28	3,44	3,08	2,9	0,59	20%
Magnesium	580293	3,12	4,96	4,56	4,2	0,97	23%
Strontium	605206	1,58	2,55	2,35	2,2	0,51	24%
Barium	226775	1,54	2,39	2,13	2,0	0,44	22%
Calcium	658507	2,1	2,9	2,3	2,5	0,42	17%
Lithium	21799998	1,80	3,52	3,07	2,8	0,89	32%
Ammonium	17636	2,84	5,19	3,61	3,9	1,20	31%

Table 11 Determined concentration of the cations in spiked sample 3

Spiked sample 3							
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Conc. III (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Zinc	86170	2,1	3,4	2,7	2,8	0,66	24%
Sodium	7857947	4,01	5,96	5,38	5,1	1,00	20%
Potassium	9763864	2,15	3,25	2,92	2,8	0,57	20%
Magnesium	510418	2,64	4,26	3,92	3,6	0,86	24%
Strontium	576250	1,51	2,42	2,24	2,1	0,48	24%
Barium	211703	1,45	2,24	2,00	1,9	0,40	21%
Calcium	590409	1,9	2,6	2,1	2,2	0,38	17%
Lithium	21101614	1,64	3,32	2,92	2,6	0,88	33%
Ammonium	15477	2,29	4,37	3,01	3,2	1,05	33%

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The Netherlands Forensic Institute

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Table 12 Determined concentration of the cations in spiked sample 4

Spiked sample 4							
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Conc. III (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Zinc	86753	2,2	3,5	2,7	2,8	0,66	24%
Sodium	7481546	3,76	5,62	5,08	4,8	0,95	20%
Potassium	9129722	1,97	3,00	2,71	2,6	0,53	21%
Magnesium	487432	2,48	4,02	3,71	3,4	0,82	24%
Strontium	663095	1,74	2,81	2,58	2,4	0,57	24%
Barium	185761	1,30	1,97	1,78	1,7	0,34	20%
Calcium	483864	1,5	2,2	1,8	1,8	0,32	18%
Lithium	18412362	1,01	2,53	2,33	2,0	0,83	42%
Ammonium	15946	2,41	4,55	3,14	3,4	1,09	32%

Table 13 Determined concentration of the cations in spiked sample 5

Spiked sample 5							
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Conc. III (ppm)	Average conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Zinc	77317	1,8	3,0	2,3	2,4	0,62	26%
Sodium	7023817	3,46	5,20	4,70	4,5	0,90	20%
Potassium	8827957	1,88	2,88	2,61	2,5	0,52	21%
Magnesium	473023	2,38	3,88	3,58	3,3	0,79	24%
Strontium	646517	1,69	2,74	2,52	2,3	0,55	24%
Barium	199479	1,38	2,11	1,90	1,8	0,37	21%
Calcium	545750	1,8	2,4	2,0	2,1	0,36	17%
Lithium	19579060	1,28	2,87	2,59	2,2	0,85	38%
Ammonium	14713	2,10	4,08	2,80	3,0	1,00	33%

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Table 14 Determined concentration of the cations in spiked sample 6

Spiked sample 6							
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Conc. III (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Zinc	72831	1,6	2,8	2,2	2,2	0,60	27%
Sodium	6968863	3,42	5,15	4,66	4,4	0,89	20%
Potassium	8018409	1,66	2,57	2,34	2,2	0,47	22%
Magnesium	441021	2,16	3,55	3,29	3,0	0,74	25%
Strontium	501028	1,31	2,07	1,94	1,8	0,41	23%
Barium	163086	1,17	1,74	1,58	1,5	0,29	19%
Calcium	350998	1,1	1,6	1,3	1,4	0,26	19%
Lithium	17272008	0,74	2,20	2,08	1,7	0,81	48%
Ammonium	15532	2,31	4,39	3,03	3,2	1,06	33%

Table 15 Determined concentration of the cations in spiked sample 7

Spiked sample 7							
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Conc. III (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Zinc	61547	1,2	2,3	1,7	1,7	0,55	32%
Sodium	6696863	3,24	4,90	4,44	4,2	0,86	20%
Potassium	7662010	1,56	2,43	2,23	2,1	0,46	22%
Magnesium	421865	2,02	3,36	3,11	2,8	0,71	25%
Strontium	521285	1,36	2,17	2,02	1,8	0,43	23%
Barium	147359	1,08	1,57	1,45	1,4	0,25	19%
Calcium	346680	1,1	1,6	1,3	1,3	0,25	19%
Lithium	17157782	0,71	2,17	2,06	1,6	0,81	49%
Ammonium	14130	1,96	3,86	2,64	2,8	0,96	34%

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The Netherlands Forensic Institute

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Table 16 Determined concentration of the cations in spiked sample 8

Spiked sample 8							
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Conc. III (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Zinc	48777	0,7	1,7	1,2	1,2	0,50	42%
Sodium	6250499	2,94	4,49	4,08	3,8	0,80	21%
Potassium	7339501	1,47	2,30	2,12	2,0	0,44	22%
Magnesium	386929	1,78	3,00	2,79	2,5	0,65	26%
Strontium	478160	1,25	1,97	1,85	1,7	0,39	23%
Barium	162126	1,17	1,73	1,57	1,5	0,29	19%
Calcium	358961	1,1	1,7	1,4	1,4	0,26	19%
Lithium	18008204	0,91	2,41	2,24	1,9	0,82	44%
Ammonium	11900	1,40	3,02	2,02	2,1	0,82	38%

Table 17 Determined concentration of the cations in spiked sample 9

Spiked sample 9							
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Conc. III (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Zinc	58958	1,1	2,1	1,6	1,6	0,54	34%
Sodium	7119222	3,52	5,29	4,78	4,5	0,91	20%
Potassium	10176344	2,26	3,41	3,06	2,9	0,59	20%
Magnesium	675213	3,77	5,93	5,43	5,0	1,13	22%
Strontium	722756	1,89	3,08	2,82	2,6	0,62	24%
Barium	228323	1,55	2,41	2,15	2,0	0,44	22%
Calcium	553015	1,8	2,5	2,0	2,1	0,36	17%
Lithium	25078938	2,57	4,48	3,78	3,6	0,97	27%
Ammonium	14803	2,13	4,11	2,82	3,0	1,01	33%

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Author: S. S. Soeknandan 120308
The Netherlands Forensic Institute

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Table 18 Determined concentration of the cations in spiked sample 10

Spiked sample 10							
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Conc. III (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Zinc	62958	1,2	2,3	1,8	1,8	0,56	31%
Sodium	6028185	2,79	4,29	3,90	3,7	0,78	21%
Potassium	7233040	1,44	2,26	2,09	1,9	0,43	22%
Magnesium	356129	1,57	2,69	2,51	2,3	0,60	27%
Strontium	438016	1,14	1,79	1,69	1,5	0,35	23%
Barium	130693	0,99	1,40	1,30	1,2	0,22	17%
Calcium	328820	1,0	1,5	1,3	1,3	0,24	19%
Lithium	16601815	0,58	2,00	1,94	1,5	0,80	53%
Ammonium	11234	1,23	2,76	1,84	1,9	0,77	40%

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Author: S. S. Soeknandan 120308
The Netherlands Forensic Institute

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10.2 Data of chemical blanks

Table 19 Determined concentration of the cations in the chemical blank 2

Chemical blank 2						
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Sodium	3856533	2,3	2,6	2,5	0,16	6%
Potassium	2491646	0,5	0,6	0,6	0,06	10%
Calcium	20349	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,03	13%

Table 20 Determined concentration of the cations in the chemical blank 3

Chemical blank 3						
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Sodium	3276508	1,8	2,0	1,9	0,12	6%
Potassium	2553144	0,6	0,6	0,6	0,06	10%
Calcium	1162	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,01	4%

Table 21 Determined concentration of the cations in the chemical blank 4

Chemical blank 4						
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Sodium	3447371	2,0	2,1	2,1	0,13	6%
Potassium	2520221	0,5	0,6	0,6	0,06	10%
Calcium	30014	0,2	0,3	0,3	0,05	18%

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The Netherlands Forensic Institute

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Table 22 Determined concentration of the cations in the chemical blank 5

Chemical blank 5						
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Sodium	3734005	2,2	2,4	2,3	0,15	6%
Potassium	2743943	0,6	0,7	0,7	0,06	10%
Calcium	1219	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,01	4%

Table 23 Determined concentration of the cations in the chemical blank 6

Chemical blank 6						
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Sodium	3529382	2,0	2,2	2,1	0,14	6%
Potassium	2078420	0,4	0,5	0,4	0,05	11%

Table 24 Determined concentration of the cations in the chemical blank 7

Chemical blank 7						
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Sodium	3673763	2,2	2,4	2,3	0,15	6%
Potassium	1873465	0,3	0,4	0,3	0,04	12%
Calcium	1572	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,00	3%

Table 25 Determined concentration of the cations in the chemical blank 8

Chemical blank 8						
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Sodium	3773307	2,3	2,5	2,4	0,15	6%
Potassium	1838363	0,3	0,4	0,3	0,04	12%
Calcium	16398	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,02	11%

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Table 26 Determined concentration of the cations in the chemical blank 9

Chemical blank 9						
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Sodium	2509458	1,1	1,2	1,1	0,07	6%
Potassium	3826146	1,0	1,1	1,1	0,09	9%
Calcium	29365	0,2	0,3	0,3	0,05	17%

Table 27 Determined concentration of the cations in the chemical blank 10

Chemical blank 10						
Cation	Area	Conc. I (ppm)	Conc. II (ppm)	Average Conc. (ppm)	STDEV	rel. STDEV
Sodium	2316612	0,9	1,0	1,0	0,05	5%
Potassium	1942540	0,3	0,4	0,4	0,04	11%
Calcium	5506	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,00	2%

11 Appendix II: Calibration curves

Calibration curves of the spiked samples and chemical blanks.

Figure 5 Calibration curve 3 of Barium

Figure 6 Calibration curve of Lithium with a concentration range of 0 to 10ppm. The linear range for this ion is smaller than the other ions.

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The Netherlands Forensic Institute

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Figure 7 Calibration curve of Lithium with range of 0 to 1ppm. Note that the correlation coefficient is better than the calibration curve with a range of 0 to 10ppm.

Figure 8 Calibration curve of Lead in the chemical blank. In the chemical blanks there was no lead present.

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Figure 9 Calibration curve of Strontium in the chemical blanks. There was no strontium present in the chemical blank samples.

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The Netherlands Forensic Institute

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12 Appendix III: Chromatograms

Figure 10 This is a chromatogram of chemical blank 1. Sodium is obvious present if compared figure 10 and figure 11.

Figure 11 This is a chromatogram of a blank (ultrapure water). No sodium present.